

Test results of diaphragm pump using 2-inch discharge and suction pipes with 25.4 x 25.4-inch boxes (no. of strokes taken at normal operating conditions). Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

Observation (no.)	Vertical lift (m)	Frictional loss (m)	Total head (m)	Length of stroke (cm)	Discharge (liter/stroke)	Strokes (no./min)	Discharge (liter/min)	Discharge (liter/h)
1	1.86	1.05	2.9	5.8	5.4	65	348	20,893
2	2.79	0.93	3.1	5.8	5.4	62	303	19,732
3	3.70	0.68	4.4	5.8	5.4	50	265	15,897

farmers can buy one to irrigate their fragmented holdings. The pump can be handled by only two men. Its most significant feature is ease of operating. Even unskilled persons can operate it and repair it with locally available inner tubes.

The pump may help to extend the area of modern rice cultivation in Bangladesh, which is seriously handicapped because of nonavailability or high cost of irrigation water during the boro (winter) season. *W*

that are easy to incorporate into F₁ hybrids.

The success of using hybrids for rice production depends on the ability to multiply the male-sterile lines and to mass-produce hybrid seed. Valuable developments in China include the use of more female plants (rows), tearing of the leaf sheath that encloses the panicle, cutting the flag leaves, applying growth regulators, and supplementary pollination. In Hunan, 3,300 ha of hybrid seed produced an average of 530 kg hybrid seed/ha. In Han-yan county, 465 ha produced 750 kg seed/ha. Because hybrid rice has high tillering ability, only 1 or 2 seedlings/hill are planted. Only 7.5 to 15 kg seed/ha are needed for planting, so 1 ha of a hybrid seed farm supplies enough seed to plant from 30 to 50 ha of farm fields. Hybrid rice is now growing or is being tested on large areas in Kiangsi, Kwangtung, Kwangsi, Fukien, Hsinking, and Liaoning provinces, as well as in Hunan. Yields have increased significantly in these regions.

Problems that remain to be resolved or improved upon include:

1. The male-sterile cytoplasm of both indica and keng (japonica) rices comes from wild rice or from ordinary cultivars. The use of hybrid rice is still limited because of the difficulties of obtaining the restorers and the insufficient combinations with strong hybrid vigor. By crossing the variety Ping-ai 58 (female) with a wild rice from South China and then making other crosses, a sterile line of "type 0" (like type 0 blood) was recently developed in Kiangsi. Its sterility is stable and many restorers have been found. In fact, many keng or indica rices can be used as restorers and they have strong hybrid vigor.

2. The most common hybrid rices, Nan-u 1, Nan-u 2, and Nan-u 3, have low disease resistance, which should be improved.

3. The long growth duration of the hybrid rices now used make them unsuitable for the cropping patterns in many areas.

Chemically and naturally male-sterile lines have been used to develop hybrid

Too late for

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Rice breeding in China

Notes from a seminar given by Mr. Lin Shih-Cheng, plant breeder and member of the Rice Research Team of the Agricultural Association of The Peoples Republic of China, visiting IRRI, 17 October 1977

Rice breeding in the People's Republic of China recently reached a new plateau with the exploitation of hybrid vigor, or heterosis, to increase yields. Because rice is a self-pollinated crop, to exploit the hybrid vigor of the F₁ for rice production, one must find three lines for seed production – the cytoplasmic male-sterile line or A-line, the maintainer or Bline, and the fertility-restorer or R-line.

The program in China to utilize hybrid vigor began in 1964 when instructors and students at the Chan-yang Agricultural School, Hunan province, found a male sterile rice plant in a field and began to study it. To obtain three lines, they crossed the male-sterile plant with thousands of cultivars but were unable to find a maintainer.

In 1970, an instructor at the Chan-yang School discovered a wild male-sterile rice plant on Hainan island. By continuously backcrossing it with cultivated varieties, and selecting progeny lines, stable male-sterile lines and

maintainer lines were developed by 1972.

In 1973, after testing many crosses, the Kiangsi Agricultural College found a restorer with strong hybrid vigor. At the same time, several other restorers with strong hybrid vigor were isolated; Restorer 1 (Thai 1) was isolated in Kiangsi province; Restorer 2 (IR24), in Kwangtung; and Restorer 3 (IR661), in Hunan. The major hybrids have been tested in different areas with good results. In 1976, hybrid rice was planted on 133,000 ha in China – 87,000 ha were in Hunan. The hybrids generally yielded from 20 to 30% higher than conventional varieties. In some fields, yields reached about 10 t/ha. Yields of 11.3 to 12 t/ha have been reported.

Hybrid rices have strong root systems, high absorption capacity, high tillering ability, high vegetative vigor, and large panicles. During later growth, the dry matter accumulation is far higher than respiration losses. For that reason, hybrid rice yields higher than conventional varieties under the same environmental conditions.

Hybrid rice offers better chances for incorporating multiple disease and insect resistance and for increasing the spectrum of resistance to certain diseases such as blast because the resistance to most major pests is controlled by dominant genes

vigor in China. Using chemically male-sterile rice has the following advantages: 1) Selection and maintenance of natural male-sterile lines is not necessary; 2) Male parents may be freely used, which extends the possible combinations and facilitates the selection of lines with strong hybrid vigor; 3) Because the F_2 seeds will not segregate into sterile and nonsterile lines, its hybrid vigor can still be used.

Chemical emasculation, using zinc methyl arsenate, is extensively used in Kwangtung, Kwangsi, Kiangsi, and other provinces. The chemical is sprayed on leaves and stems at booting stage. When the chemical is properly used, 90% or more of the plants are sterilized. But efficiency is low if the chemical is used improperly, or if rain falls after application.

The most common breeding method used in China is hybridization followed by pedigree selection. In the 1960's many research stations used radiation or mutation breeding, and developed some good varieties. Haploid breeding was initiated and widely used in the 1970's to shorten the breeding cycles. Some institutes have successfully simplified the culture medium, to enhance breeding by farmers. Research has been conducted on autotetraploid breeding, but no promising varieties have yet been developed. Distant or intergeneric hybridization has also been tried, such as corn-rice or bamboo-rice. Although cytogenetic studies are not yet complete, highly heritable variations are found in such distant crosses. For example, the progeny of bamboo-rice crosses is a perennial with a very hard stem.

CORRECTION: Table accompanying the item *Weed competition in transplanted rice*, IRRN 2:3 (June 1977) by Sadeli Suriapermana, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Sukamandi, Indonesia, should read:

Effect of competition from various weed species on number of productive tillers and grain yield of transplanted rice IR34.

Competing weed species	Weed weight 70 DT ^a (t/ha)	Productive rice tillers (no./hill)	Rice yield (t/ha)
<i>Salvinia natans</i>	1.0	16.0	4.4
None	0	13.4	4.2
<i>Marsilea minuta</i>	2.5	13.7	3.4
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	1.4	11.2	3.1
<i>Cyperus</i> sp.	4.5	9.6	2.9
<i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	4.6	9.3	2.4
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	7.6	7.1	2.4
<i>M. vaginalis</i> + <i>Cyperus</i> sp.	9.8	7.5	2.3
<i>Cyperus</i> sp. + <i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	8.9	8.0	2.3
<i>M. vaginalis</i> + <i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	6.3	7.6	2.0
All + natural weed flora	6.5	8.8	1.9

^aDT = days after transplanting.

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